

This is the dream set, which goes as followed:

- The portal set place, 0 dreams paired 0 dreams, and the extra 0th dream, which make the outcome of another 0th dream
- The extra dimension set place, 1 dream paired 1 dream, and the extra 1st dream, which make the outcome of another 1st dream.
- The geometry set place, 2 dreams paired 2 dreams, and the extra 2nd dream, which make the outcome of another 2nd dream.
- The membrane set place, 3 dreams paired 3 dreams, and the extra 3rd dream, which make the outcome of another 3rd dream.
- The nightmare set place, 4 dreams paired 4 dreams, and the extra 4th dream, which make the outcome of another 4th dream.
- The escape set place, 5 dreams paired 5 dreams, and the extra 5th dream, which make the outcome of another 5th dream.
- The map set place, 6 dreams paired 6 dreams, and the extra 6th dream, which make the outcome of another 6th dream.

Set.